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THE INFLUENCE AND ROLE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF EDUCATION

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Abstract

The role of information and communication technologies used in education is discussed in the research work. These ICT tools play an extremely important role in the development of society. One of the possibilities of using ICT in the current period is education. At almost every stage of the learner's development, ICT is definitely used. The "Program for provision of general education schools in the Republic of Azerbaijan with information and communication technologies (2005-2007)" approved by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Mr. Ilham Aliyev on August 21, 2004, started this process in our country. After that, the "State Program for Informatization of the Education System in the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2008-2012", adopted by the head of the country on June 10, 2008, aims to establish a qualitatively new education model in our country in accordance with international standards using ICT, a single electronic education space. set the main goal of creating and integrating the education system into the world education space.

The main goals related to the informatization of the education system have already been defined, and a large number of planned measures have been implemented. One of the significant events is that the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan declared 2010 as the "Year of ICT in Education" in our country, and within the framework of this campaign, conferences, seminars, various stimulating and motivating actions, competitions are held. It is commendable that various funds, companies and firms are closely involved in these works. Supplying schools with ICT equipment, including computers, laptops, and interactive boards, is currently being successfully continued.

Keywords: information, communication, technology, knowledge, teacher-student unity.

Relevance of the topic: The 21st century consists of a digital world, and information and communication technologies (ICT) are used in all areas of this world. In modern times, the development of information and communication technologies (ICT) is one of the important indicators of the intellectual and scientific potential of every country, and the necessity of this process is more felt in the current globalization era. The rapid development and spread of these technologies creates wide opportunities for the development of mankind. We know that information technology is changing day by day and developing rapidly. These technologies require future professionals to be flexible and constantly ready to adapt to this technology. The rapid development of computer technology from year to year allows us to conclude that From the beginning of the 21st century, information storage in all developed countries will be based only on paperless technology. Informatics is the science of information transformation, based on the use of computing techniques, and provides knowledge about the creation and operation of information systems. This knowledge connects the collection, processing, transmission and use of information with the application of computing techniques. The application of computing techniques,

in turn, involves new man-machine technology. The role of information technologies in the process of economic management is irreplaceable. Informatics as a field of science can realize its possibilities after the information model of the studied phenomenon is established. Informatics develops the general methodological principles of building this model.

Interpretation of the research: Today, as the world economy takes a line of development based on knowledge, it requires the establishment of a system that meets these requirements from the educational systems of the countries. Therefore, it is required to develop not only the mechanisms that meet the socio-economic requirements of the country, but also the mechanisms that meet the competition of the global world as a whole. Serious and successful steps have been taken in the field of informatization in our republic. National leader Heydar Aliyev approved the "National Strategy on Information and Communication Technologies for the Development of the Republic of Azerbaijan (2003-2012)" on the wide application and development of information and communication technologies in our republic with the Order No. 1146 dated February 17, 2003. has done This has been considered as the direction with the highest priority

among the application directions of ICT for the educational field of Azerbaijan. Important steps have already been taken in the direction of modernization of education and application of information technologies in education in Azerbaijan.

Wide application of modern ICT in our country aims to create a uniform nationwide educational environment and provide opportunities for quality education for all sections of the population.

Now ICT is not only a way to provide educational process. ICT opens up new opportunities to ensure the student's independent understanding. In this regard, the role of the teacher also changes: he becomes a consultant, coordinator of the educational process. Its purpose is to support and develop decision-making

skills in schoolchildren, to understand and judge the purpose of the studied topics. These are quite difficult pedagogical tasks - their significance cannot be underestimated. Here, ICT plays the role of a catalyst, they help push children to new knowledge. If the content of this or that topic is clear to the student, his question may arise: exactly what and why should be studied. At the root of the desire for knowledge is vital interest: what knowledge do I need most, with the help of which methods can I get this knowledge. Thus, ICT acts as a bridge between the pursuit of knowledge and the decision of other vital issues. Once a student understands the role education plays in his or her life, he or she will feel more motivated to continue studying.

When applying the use of information and communication technologies its irreplaceable, new possibilities are showing themselves in a useful way. These are interactivity between teacher and student during teaching, efficient use of time, saving time, students more optimally and objectively

is the result of evaluation. Information and communication in the modern world application of technologies (ICT) to teaching has become an integral part of education. Already it is impossible to imagine educational institutions without information and communication technologies. The use of computers in education helps to create an information environment for the student who is interested in everything and tries to get more and deeper information. The computer plays the role of an electronic intermediary between the teacher and the student, makes the teaching process more interesting, colorful, visual, and intensifies it. It is known that the implementation of a modern and interactive educational model using ICT puts new demands on the school and the teaching staff. It is impossible to achieve the effective application of ICT in the educational system without increasing the ICT

literacy of the pedagogical staff and forming an innovative approach to the teaching-learning process. The successful and efficient implementation of the changes arising from the requirements of the modern era in schools automatically necessitates a different approach to the teaching process by the teacher. For this reason, it is a necessary process for teachers to acquire ICT skills and use ICT skills as a pedagogical tool in the teaching process. (5;56)

It is very important to find ways to properly use ICT in education and to improve these skills. It should be noted that the most optimal way to master the knowledge of information and communication technologies (ICT) is through high school. Mastering these technologies during school years ensures their active participation in building the information society. Student information with the help of information and communication technologies he tries to get free, his thinking and psychological skills develop. Most importantly, the student becomes an active participant in the learning process. At the same time, the use of computer technologies frees the teacher from being the only source of information that tells the truth for

students, he becomes a collaborator for the student. The application of ICT during teaching has also created many opportunities for the teacher. Thus, it saves time in class, conveys information accurately, uses various technical training tools at the same time, conveys a larger amount of information, models various processes, especially those that cannot be implemented in school laboratories. In addition, it presents information in any form - graph, table, picture, helps the teacher to use the methodical methods developed by his colleagues and their application, uses ready-made work according to the lesson. According to these indicators, teaching with information and communication technologies is superior to the traditional teaching method. At present, teachers emphasize that the application of ICT in teaching gives positive results. So, since the application of new technologies in teaching revives the lesson, even the weakest student in the class is not left out of the process. Making the lesson more interesting thanks to the application of information technologies directs the attention of any student to teaching. (5;58) At present, teachers emphasize that the application of ICT in teaching gives positive results. So, since the application of new technologies in teaching revives the lesson, even the weakest student in the class is not left out of the process. Making the lesson more interesting thanks to the application of information technologies directs the attention of any student to teaching. (5;58) At present, teachers emphasize that the application of ICT in teaching gives positive results. So, since the application of new technologies in teaching revives the lesson, even the weakest student in the class is not left out of the process. Making the lesson more interesting thanks to the application of information technologies directs the attention of any student to teaching. (5;58)

The way of continuous education of students goes through continuous education of teachers. In connection with the use of ICT in school practice, the role of the teacher should change. The main reasons for such changes are:

- * The teacher's role should not be limited to the transfer of information to students. It should support and stimulate critical and creative thinking in children, help the development of computer literacy, develop teamwork skills, teach them to communicate effectively and act successfully in different situations.

- * The online test system helps the teacher to adequately assess the students' knowledge level.

- * In order to meet the learning needs of the students, it is necessary for the teachers to review the teaching methods and curriculum from the point of view of compliance with the requirements of the modern era.

- * With the involvement of ICT in the teaching process, some of the traditional teaching resources will no longer be needed and they will go out of circulation.

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skills in schoolchildren, to understand and judge the purpose of the studied topics. These are quite difficult pedagogical tasks - their significance cannot be underestimated. Here, ICT plays the role of a catalyst, they help push children to new knowledge. If the content of this or that topic is clear to the student, his question may arise: exactly what and why should be studied. At the root of the desire for knowledge is vital interest: what knowledge do I need most, with the help of which methods can I get this knowledge. Thus, ICT acts as a bridge between the pursuit of knowledge and the decision of other vital issues. Once a student understands the role education plays in his or her life, he or she will feel more motivated to continue studying. The computer classrooms intended for teaching various subjects should become the core of the school. Therefore, schools should be equipped with the necessary number of computer classrooms for permanent and efficient use of ICT in the teaching of various subjects. Conditions should be created for the maximum use of computer classes, and a mechanism for efficient use of their capabilities should be developed during extracurricular hours. (5; 23) The computer classrooms intended for teaching various subjects should become the core of the school. Therefore, schools should be equipped with the necessary number of computer classrooms for permanent and efficient use of ICT in the teaching of various subjects. Conditions should be created for the maximum use of computer classes, and a mechanism for efficient use of their capabilities should be developed during extracurricular hours. (5; 23) The computer classrooms intended for teaching various subjects should become the core of the school. Therefore, schools should be equipped with the necessary number of computer classrooms for permanent and efficient use of ICT in the teaching of various subjects. Conditions should be created for the maximum use of computer classes, and a mechanism for efficient use of their capabilities should be developed during extracurricular hours. (5; 23)

Now we would like to touch on some aspects of the use of information and communication technologies in schools. The fundamental knowledge chosen by the teachers, not only in the field of pedagogy and psychology, but also when successfully using new technologies greatly simplifies the educational process, makes it dynamic and flexible. Adding a computer to the teaching model "teacher-student-classroom" allows organizing the educational process according to an individual program, stimulating the child's interest and desire for lessons. Computer lessons are very attractive and memorable for children. Multimedia tools, automated educational systems, computer educational programs, animated graphics, colorful illustrations have a positive effect on the cognitive activity of students and significantly improve the quality of their results at Olympiads, various intellectual competitions.

Surveys conducted with students also prove that the use of ICT in teaching increases their self-confidence and interest in the subject. As we know, the psychological state of the students in the class is different. There are students who think that their

answers are wrong during the lesson, shy away from their peers and the teacher and refuse to answer, thus becoming more passive. A student sitting in front of a personal computer no longer avoids this device, there is feedback between him and the computer, he enters the answers he thinks into the computer, sees his mistakes, corrects them with the help of the computer, avoids negative emotions, and as a result, his self-confidence increases. When using a personal computer, each student has the opportunity to re-watch the explanation if they do not understand the given topic and repeat it until they understand it.

ICT increases the possibilities of receiving information through vision, so it realizes the description of objects that are invisible to the naked eye and change their color and shape. Assignments in the

form of videos or animations accompanied by good text and beautiful music have a strong impact on the student, and lead to the development of his artistic taste and better mastery of the material. Thus, ICT not only develops the intellectual capabilities of a person, but also creates new development perspectives, a new global cultural system, and opens up interesting opportunities for improving the quality of education. The use of ICT in training and the creation of educational networks is an important condition for the further development of education. First of all, the wide application of ICT carries the teacher's goal and duty. Second, the creation of an educational environment at school creates opportunities for participation in educational knowledge.

It is considered one of the important issues to study the process of interdisciplinary communication, to improve and implement the methodology of related teaching of subjects. Starting from high school, in order to increase the interest of students in various subjects, to absorb information quickly and effectively, it is recommended that informatics and other subject teachers take any general subject in two and in some cases three subjects in the form of joint - integrative lessons. For example, fun mathematics, geography, chemistry, life science, elements of geometry, etc. taught in the primary classes of modern private schools. some subjects in the subjects can be taught jointly by the teacher who teaches those subjects and the informatics teacher. Teaching informatics and information technologies in connection with other subjects has great potential for deepening students' knowledge. For this, when preparing programs and textbooks for individual classes, the subject of informatics and information technologies of that class should be taken into account, and hours should be allocated for integrative lessons in these programs. A number of subject teachers do not pay enough attention to the problem of interdisciplinary communication. It is known from experience that, in addition to their subject, teachers who know other related subjects at a certain level have higher educational achievements. The main reason for this is that those teachers teach their lessons as if they were teachers of several subjects. A number of subject teachers do not pay enough attention to the problem of interdisciplinary communication. It is known from experience that, in

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The computer classrooms intended for teaching various subjects should become the core of the school. Therefore, schools should be equipped with the necessary number of computer classrooms for the permanent and efficient use of ICT in the teaching of various subjects. Conditions should be created for the maximum use of computer classrooms, and a mechanism for the effective use of their capabilities should be developed during extracurricular hours.

The main goal of informatization of the education system is modern information it is to train personalities with culture, to form a uniform educational and informational environment in the country. This environment provides the following by using new information technologies:

- Increasing the quality of education;
- Formation of new information culture;
- Equalization of opportunities for citizens to study at all levels;

-Ensuring the integration of the education system into the information, culture and education space of the world.

In order to achieve these goals, it is necessary to comprehensively solve the following important tasks:

-Ensuring the integration of information technologies into the educational process. Preparation of national electronic textbooks and their application in the educational process, integration with traditional textbooks, as well as preparation of auxiliary methodical tools. Quality assurance, standardization and certification of educational information technology tools;

-Creation of a unified education-information system. This system should connect all levels of education and information systems, as well as management, service, scientific-research, methodical-educational and technological centers of education;

- Creation of an effective and transparent monitoring system and resource center based on ICT for education management;

-Establishing a system for training pedagogical and ICT personnel for educational institutions. Teaching them the ability to use the latest information technologies in the educational process. Creating an opportunity to acquire ICT skills for all participants of the educational process;

- Provision of educational institutions with modern ICT equipment and Internet/Intranet network;

- Development of terminology in the field of ICT and its application as a single standard;

- Preparation of scientific support for the process of informatization of education and modern training methods based on information technologies;

- Creation of a unified information infrastructure of the state management and regulatory system in the field of education;

-Implementation of complex measures to ensure information security and eliminate dangerous situations. (3;2)

Although the application of information technology in the education system of most countries of the world has led to many innovations, we still face problems that are difficult to solve in the informatization of schools. It should be noted that improving the education system in our country based on ICT has always been the focus of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan Mr. Ilham Aliyev. "The Program for provision of general education schools in the Republic of Azerbaijan with information and communication technologies" (2005-2007 years), "The State Program for informatization of the education system in the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2008-2012" constitute the main milestones in the informatization of our national education.

The Ministry of Education announced 2010 as the "Year of ICT in Education" in our country, and within the framework of this campaign, conferences, seminars, various stimulating and motivating actions, competitions were held. The "State Strategy for the Development of Education in the Republic of Azerbaijan", approved by the order of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated October 24, 2013, set

the informatization of education as an important task. All this is the result of the great concern of our state for the development of education.

In its recommendations, UNESCO proposes three approaches to school informatization. The first approach called "application of ICT to education" requires teachers to increase the effectiveness of students' ICT skills in the learning process. The second approach called "Assimilation of knowledge" sets demands on teachers such as deep mastery of the subjects of education and application of this knowledge in solving problems encountered in the real world. According to the third approach, "Information production", teachers should help future citizens and workers to produce new knowledge necessary for the harmonious development and prosperity of society.

Modern teacher:

1. should teach the student the ways of learning, they are necessary for him freely information from the right sources and without wasting time to search, to systematize the information found and more useful for himself selecting information, analyzing selected information and obtained

making the information his own and expressing his personal attitude to the matter should form skills;

2. Instill in the student a sense of self-confidence and his own opinions in front of the audience should form the ability of free presentation;

3. for the implementation of the above in the teaching of any subject should constantly direct students to use new information technologies.

The use of interactive whiteboards and virtual laboratory programs in the teaching process ensures one of the main principles of the lesson, its visibility. By gently touching the sensitive surface of the electronic board with a special pen or finger, all possible operations on the computer can be performed on it in interactive mode. An electronic board, a microscope connected to a computer, a scanner, a digital camera, a video camera, etc. displays the images received from the devices on the screen in an enlarged form. Students can follow the explanation of any chemical reaction, physical, biological, geographical processes through a virtual laboratory program. This greatly enlivens the teaching by integrating the theoretical and methodological knowledge, practical skills and experience of the students, and increases the ability of the students to have a creative approach, thinking, initiative, and a deep understanding of the teaching material.

One advantage of the interactive whiteboard is that it allows you to save all the operations performed on it in video format and use it many times. Such opportunities are especially important for students who miss classes for various reasons or children who fall behind in education. So, if the student is unable to participate, if the lesson process is not completely clear, or those who fall behind in the training, they can watch the material repeatedly on the computer until they fully understand it. In e-learning, all students are eager to go to the blackboard and perform all the tasks of the teacher. Lessons held (taught) in interactive mode enable all students, including those who are passive,

shy, or have certain physical or psychological disabilities, to actively participate in the learning process.

The inclusion of ICT in the educational system, informatization of the educational process requires all educators to acquire new skills and habits. Teachers must be able to implement the following teaching methods or a combination of them: coordinated activity, teacher-learner interview, expository teaching, and consultative (consultative) teaching. Let's look at the essence of the indicated training methods:

Coordinated action The solution begins with the setting of a complex (general) problem, which is realized with the participation of groups of students. At this time, each learner in the groups takes on a slightly specialized role. In the process of solving the problem, it is important to coordinate the activities of learners aimed at quickly and optimally reaching the set goal. This approach is usually best implemented through project-based learning and business games options can be realized by applying ICT tools.

In the process of interviewing the learner and the teacher, the initiative is alternately taken by both the teacher (whose goal is to identify the gap in the learner's knowledge) and the teacher (who formulates questions to deepen their knowledge). In this type of learning process, the learner's knowledge can be analyzed in the course of the dialogue. Although the implementation of the interview in ICT is a very difficult and time-consuming process, its implementation allows a more accurate assessment of the learner's knowledge, unlike mechanical learning.

In explanatory training, the learner is presented with numerous examples of problem solving, and the meaning of all elements of knowledge is explained in the process of obtaining the final result. The training process is presented as a process of continuous revitalization of knowledge. The importance of acquiring new knowledge must be understood by the learner, and each quantum of new knowledge must be accompanied by new opportunities. Such an approach also involves the opposite activity of opening simpler or already known concepts according to the terms according to the field of study. Expository teaching takes a lot of effort on the part of the teacher, which quickly tires both the learner and the teacher. Therefore, the use of computer programs that work with those principles in the teaching process can lead to good results both in terms of the organization of teaching and in terms of engaging the interests of learners.

Counselor training implies a more active activity of the learner in the learning environment. In this learning environment, he is presented with the current issues of the studied subject and is given the opportunity for research. The intervention of ICT equipment in this process can return the results of the learner's activity (correct or incorrect) more quickly. In this case, the system can provide semantically dependent concepts or, in the case of intellectual components, guide the learner to problem solving. This mode, as a rule, is required by the user himself, and the system, the user is mainly the system he plays a more passive role, unlike in guided (teacher) training, where

he answers questions. Thus, the system turns into a material similar to an "electronic encyclopedia" that is provided in the query system. Adequate instructional support is an important component of learning environments, using both conceptual and practical knowledge, as well as the means to organize learning modes (explanation, reinforcement, diagnosis, repetition, research, etc.) to present learning material. (3;14)

Today, information is given about the program called "Crocodile Physics", which is famous all over the world. This powerful virtual laboratory software allows you to model physical phenomena, conduct virtual experiments on "Electricity and Electromagnetism", "Motion and Power", "Wave Phenomena" and "Optics".

"Crocodile Physics" is very useful for physics teachers to conduct laboratory experiments with students and is rich with ready-made examples that meet today's demand. "Crocodile Physics" is a program that is very useful and provided with ready-made examples that teachers teaching physics at school can use with students to conduct laboratory experiments according to today's demand and get the desired result. "Crocodile Physics" electronic laboratory program contains more than 46 ready-made practice examples, which are ready-made practice examples that correspond to International IGCSE, A-Level exam curricula.

"Crocodile chemistry" program is one of the convenient programs used in the field of chemistry. When using the program, it moved a part of the operations we did in the laboratory to the virtual environment. Program allows the teacher to master the teaching material in more detail by conducting any experiment in the course of the lesson, etc.

ChemOffice software package includes ChemDraw, ChemFinder, Database Subscriptions, Chem3D programs. Those programs allow the teacher to visually show the physical properties of chemical substances, their spatial structure, and the connection between molecules.

Of course, these are not all factors affecting the quality of education. At present, work is ongoing in the direction of creating new, modern technologies in this direction.

CONCLUSION

The results obtained during the systematic application of information and communication technologies in education show that the environment of information technologies in education is fully it transforms, allows interactive Organization of the lesson process. As a result of the wide and comprehensive application of information and communication technologies, human activity, society as a whole, is undergoing changes, completely new realities, values, socio-psychological environment are being formed. The "program of provision of secondary schools with ICT" approved by the order of the president of the Republic of Azerbaijan was the most important step in this direction. As a result, almost every school today is provided with computers. But,

